
PROPERTIES OF ROOF MATERIALS FOR LOW-COST, SUSTAINABLE HOUSING FROM RECYCLED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for affordable housing in Nigeria necessitates the development of sustainable and cost-effective building materials. Skepticism among builders and homeowners regarding the long-term performance and aesthetic appeal of roof materials made of plastics are still commonplace. This study aims to address these gaps by developing and testing these plastic composite materials. It investigates the feasibility of producing low-cost, sustainable roofing materials from recycled plastics. Recycled high density polyethylene was used to produce roofing sheets and tiles with varying plastic content (0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%) respectively; a filler (sand/calcium carbonate) was added to some of the blends. Physical and mechanical properties were tested, and cost analysis and environmental impacts were evaluated. Results showed significant improvements in tensile strength, water resistance, and thermal insulation as the plastic content increased. The mixes with high plastic content (75% and 100%) demonstrated mechanical properties adequate for roofing. Thermal insulation properties of the plastic specimens proved about 600 % better as compared to traditional roofing materials (zinc and aluminum). The recycled plastic roofing material has lower cost of about 30 percent compared to the traditional materials. This study contributes to the development of sustainable building materials, reducing plastic waste and environmental pollution in Nigeria. These findings are important for the construction industry and would lead to achieving a much-needed goal of an eco-friendly Nigeria.

Keywords: *Properties, Recycled Plastics, Low-Cost Housing, and Filler*

INTRODUCTION

The need for affordable and sustainable housing is a pressing issue globally, particularly in developing countries. In Nigeria, the housing deficit is estimated to be over seventeen million units, with many citizens struggling to access decent and affordable shelter. A significant factor contributing to the high cost of housing is the exorbitant cost of roofing materials. Roofing

materials in Nigeria reflect a mix of traditional heritage and modern functionality, each with distinct advantages and drawbacks (Akinjare, 2018). Traditional materials like asphalt shingles, clay tiles, and metal sheets are often expensive, energy-intensive to produce, and contribute significantly to waste generation, pollution, and climate change (Ogunsemi, 2006). The alarming rate of plastic waste generation in Nigeria, estimated at 2.5 million tons annually, presents both a challenge and an opportunity for innovative solutions. Recycled plastics, sourced from landfills, roadside dumps, and waterways, can be transformed into durable, low-cost, and sustainable roofing materials. Research has shown that these materials offer numerous benefits, including reduced construction costs, improved thermal insulation, enhanced durability, and minimal negative environmental impact (Al Sabahi et al., 2016). This research, therefore, focuses on harnessing the potential of recycled polyethylene to create a high-performance, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly roofing solution that can help curb plastic pollution while addressing Nigeria's housing deficit.

Traditional roofing materials includes i. thatch, which is common in rural areas and are made from grasses, palm fronds, or leaves. They are locally sourced and biodegradable, have very low fire resistance and highly limited lifespan (Ogunsemi, 2006). ii. Clay Tiles, primarily used in Northern Nigeria. They offer good thermal insulation but are heavy, brittle, and their production is energy-intensive due to kiln firing (Olanrewaju, 2012). Modern roof materials include, i. Asbestos Cement Sheets; they are widely used in the past due to durability and affordability, but their use has declined significantly due to documented health concerns (Adeleke, 2016). ii. Metal Roofing Sheets (Zinc and Aluminum): they are mostly Favoured in urban areas for their durability, ease of installation, and lightweight nature. However, they are poor thermal insulators, often leading to uncomfortably high indoor temperatures in Nigeria's tropical climate (Akinjare, 2018). iii. Concrete Tiles are durable, aesthetically pleasing, and offer good weathering resistance but are expensive and require substantial structural support due to their weight (Oyedele, 2015). Recycling plastics into building materials is an increasingly popular approach in solving both the housing deficit and plastic waste pollution concerns. The choice of recycled plastics is crucial for the final product's performance; some of which are: i. High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), known for its high strength-to-density ratio, excellent tensile strength, and water resistance (Adeyemi et

al., 2018). ii. Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), it offers flexibility and is often used in composite mixes to improve workability and impact resistance (Ogunbayo et al., 2020). iii. Polypropylene (PP) & Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), These polymers add rigidity, stability, and ultraviolet (UV) resistance when properly processed (Mwembela et al., 2019). Some benefits of Reused Plastics for Roofing include i. reduced Waste, utilizing recycled plastics decreases the volume of waste sent to landfills and reduces environmental pollution (Al Sabahi et al., 2016). They offer some similar properties to traditional tiles, making them a viable option for the construction industry (Roy & Varghese, 2018). ii. energy Efficiency, plastic roofing material requires less energy for manufacturing compared to the traditional, high-temperature processes used for clay or metal (Singh et al., 2017). iii. thermal Insulation, plastic, being poor conductor of heat, offers superior thermal insulation compared to metal, which is essential in tropical environments and iv. weather resistance, it has high resistance to moisture, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, and termite attack. The concept of using recycled plastics for building materials has gained attraction across Africa. Researchers have investigated the feasibility of using specific plastic types. Adeyemi, et al, (2018), produced HDPE-based roofing tiles in Ibadan with promising tensile strength. Ogunbayo et al, (2020) demonstrated that composite mixes of LDPE and sand exceeded load-bearing capacity requirements. Other studies have proposed systematic classification frameworks for effective use in the building sector (Iroegbu et al, 2021). Dodo, et al, (2024) appraised the use of plastic bottles as building blocks in Abuja-Nigeria. Furthermore, Adewumi (2020) highlighted a Lagos-based startup, successfully converting sachet bags into roofing tiles. The successful use of recycled plastics in community-based sustainable housing projects has also been studied (Solaja, et al, 2020).

The "Plastic Roofing Project" in South Africa has successfully provided homes for hundreds of residents using extruded plastic tiles (Mokhtar, et al, 2019). Similarly, the "Recycled Plastic Roofing Initiative" in Kenya demonstrated a successful pilot using injection-molded HDPE tiles (Gathoni et al., 2020). Plastic-Based Composites **such as** thermoformed or injection molded tiles from household plastics are weatherproof, durable, and scalable (Ogunbayo et al., 2020). Experimental studies, such as those combining waste PET and river sand, have shown promising results for composite roof tile products (Bamigboye, 2019).

The National Environmental Standards and Regulation Enforcement Agency (NESREA) oversees plastic waste regulation in Nigeria, but has not yet fully integrated waste utilization into building standards. Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON), currently, lacks a specific universally accepted standard for recycled plastics for roofing, which is a key hurdle for market adoption.

Nigerian National Housing Policy (2018) encourages locally sourced, cost-effective plastic materials for roofing; it however, does not give clear incentives for manufacturers using recycled inputs. To ensure acceptability in formal construction, the development and testing of recycled plastic materials must align with established international standards, particularly the British Standards (BS) and related Indian Standard Organisation (ISO), often referenced in Commonwealth countries like Nigeria. Recycling plastics could be sorted by type using the Resin Identification Code (RIC) as shown in Table 1. The process determines which plastics are easily recyclable and more environmentally friendly.

Table 1. Sorted plastics by Resin Identification Code (RIC)

RIC Code	Abbreviation	Full Name	Key Properties & Common Uses
1	PET or PETE	Polyethylene Terephthalate	Clear, tough, excellent gas barrier. Used for: Soda bottles, water bottles, and synthetic fibers (polyester).
2	HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene	Stiff, strong, high resistance to chemicals, used for: Milk jugs, detergent bottles, sturdy toys, and recycled roof tiles!
3	V or PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride	Hard and rigid, but can be made soft and flexible. Used for: Pipes (plumbing), window frames, wire insulation, and medical tubing.
4	LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene	Flexible, translucent, and tough (high puncture resistance). Used for: Plastic shopping bags, squeeze bottles, and plastic wraps.
5	PP	Polypropylene	Strong, very durable, and high heat tolerance. Used for: Yogurt tubs, bottle caps, reusable food containers, and car parts.

6	PS	Polystyrene	Light, rigid, can be foamed (Styrofoam) used for: Disposable cutlery, foam cups, egg cartons, and protective packaging.
7	OTHER	Other Plastics	This is a catch-all category for plastics not listed above (like polycarbonates, nylons, and multi-layer plastics). Used for: DVD, and multi-gallon water bottles.

Source (UNIDO. (2020))

Compressive and tensile strength of material are calculated using equations 1 and 2 respectively (Neville, 1996).

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A} \quad (1)$$

F = maximum applied force (N)

A = cross-sectional area (mm²)

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad (2)$$

P = load at fracture (N),

L = span length between supports (mm),

b = specimen width (mm),

d = specimen thickness (mm)

Water absorption (W_{abs}) is calculated using equation 3 (Neville, 1996).

$$Percentage\ W_{abs} = \frac{W_w - W_d}{W_d} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

W_w = Weight of Saturated Sample (g),

W_d = Weight of Oven-Dry Sample (g).

This research aims at developing low-cost, robust, and sustainable roofing materials using recycled plastics with the following specific objectives:

- i. to determine the mechanical (tensile, flexural, impact) properties of the plastics.
- ii. to test the thermal properties of the developed roof materials.
- iii. to assess the environmental impact and
- iv. to analyse the cost effectiveness of the new materials in comparison to traditional roofing materials such as galvanized steel and aluminum.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

The materials used for the study are:

- i. High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) polymer, made from soft drinks and water bottles. The waste bottles were collected from post-consumer in community recycling hubs in Gboko and Makurdi, Nigeria.
- ii. Calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) from finely ground eggshells mixed with river sand (the sand was collected from River Benue, Nigeria). The sand was used as a filler for reinforcement in composite mixes.

Method

The plastics were thoroughly cleaned using detergent and hot water to remove dirt, labels, and organic residues. They were then air-dried and manually sorted by type, using the Resin Identification Code (RIC). These codes are used to determine which plastics are easily recyclable and more environmentally friendly (Awoyera, 2020). The plastics were then shredded to a maximum size of 10mm, to ensure uniform melting and compounding. Compounding and Pelletizing Blends were prepared based on the weight percentage of plastic content versus filler (calcium carbonate). The plastic specimens to filler ratio adopted are 100:0, 75:25, 50:50, 25:75, and 0:100. The blends were compounded at 180–220 °C ensure a homogenous mix of the different polymers and additives, then pelletized for subsequent molding. Blending process was done by melting the plastic specimens in an oven at control temperatures of 180–220 °C, depending on the polymer type. The filler blend was gradually introduced and manually premixed before compounding. The mixture was extruded and pelletized to form uniform sizes for moulding.

Specimens Fabrication Process:

The samples were produced using the Compression Molding Technique. All test specimens were moulded to uniform dimensions of 200 × 200 × 10 mm. This size was deliberately chosen to fit the small-scale research work. Processing Parameters: A laboratory-grade hydraulic press was used to compact the heated composite mixture. The heating temperature was 200 °C, dwell time was 15 minutes, and the applied pressure was 5mpa. The samples were allowed to cure at ambient temperature for 24 hours. They were then removed from the moulds.

Materials Characterisation and Testing

A total of three replicates of the roof specimens were tested for each material composition. Tensile strength test was done as specified by BS EN 527-2:2012. Equation 2 was used to calculate tensile strength values; and the flexural strength test was carried out as specified by BS EN 178 (or ASTM D790). The Charpy Impact resistance test was carried out using Pendulum-type Impact Tester. The energy absorbed by the material during breakage due to impact was measured (ASTM D256, 2016). Water absorption test of the specimens was done as specified by ASTM D570. Thermal conductivity test was carried out on the specimens as specified by ASTM C177.

Statistical Analysis

Test results were statistically analysed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS. One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to compare the mean values across the different plastic blend ratios and to statistically compare the performance of the plastic mix against the traditional materials. One-Way ANOVA was utilized to test the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the mean strength property values of the Plastic and traditional Zinc and Aluminum roof specimens (Murray and Larry, 2011).

Cost-Benefit Analysis

An estimated cost analysis was conducted to establish the economic feasibility of the recycled plastic roofing materials. The total production cost (Naira/m²) included material cleaning, shredding, compounding, energy, labour, and the cost of additives. The final cost was compared to market prices for traditional roofing materials sourced from Makurdi and Abuja suppliers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the results of the measured properties of the roof specimens. It is observed that the tensile and flexural strengths increase as the content of the filler (sand or calcium carbonate) reduces. This is expected because plastics such as HDPE (High-Density Poly-Ethylene) provide continuity that allows stress transfer to occur more uniformly compared to when the filler content is high. This happens because fillers like sand and calcium carbonate interrupt the polymer chains, reducing flexibility and the ability of the material to stretch or withstand bending. As the plastic content increases, the matrix becomes more cohesive and

flexible (Bamigboye, 2019). Solaja, et al, (2020) gave tensile and flexural strengths of pure HDPE specimens as 14.25 and 32.63 Mpa respectively. Metal roofs materials example, Zinc and Aluminum have flexural strengths of 200.0 and 120.0 Mpa. They remain superior in absolute bending resistance (Soboyejo, 2002).). Water absorption reduces drastically as the plastic percentage increases. This behaviour is characteristic of thermoplastics. They are naturally hydrophobic, so increasing the polymer content creates fewer pores and pathways for water to enter. This is particularly useful in roofing applications, where water resistance is essential to durability (Neville, 1996). For roofing applications, low water absorption means less swelling, low risk of moisture-induced cracking, reduced microbial growth, and improved long-term durability.

Thermal conductivity reduces significantly in the plastic specimen, about 600 % compared to Zinc and Aluminum. This is because, polymers do not conduct heat well. This means roofs made from the plastic blends will help maintain cooler indoor temperatures, in contrast to zinc or aluminium, which absorb and transmit heat easily (Chen, et al, 2018).). The impact resistance increases with plastic content because plastic materials deform elastically under sudden loading and absorb more energy before cracking. The superior impact performance of the plastic material implies better resistance to mechanical damage from external forces, leading to lower maintenance cost and longer service life compared to thin metal sheets like Zinc and Aluminum, which are easily dented or punctured. This could also lead to sharp edges on roof materials, which are not safe, especially to humans.

Density decreases with increasing plastic percentage. This means that the roofing materials become lighter as more plastic is added. Light roofing sheets reduce dead load on buildings, which is estimated to make construction easier and potentially lowering structural cost requirements. The density of 980 kg/m³ obtained is notably low, positioning the material as an ultra-lightweight material. (Neville, 1996). The density is significantly lower than the 1,075 kg/m³ reported for some plastic/sand composites (Oladele, et al, 2017), offering substantial advantages in handling, and transportation. The results show that the 75% and 100% plastic mixes provide adequate strength, durability, and thermal performance, making them suitable for roofing applications. Though plastic specimen is less strong compared to metals in tensile and flexural strengths, they

outperform the later in key areas that matter for comfort, impact resistance, and environmental sustainability.

Table 2. Results of Properties of the Roof Specimen

Material Mix	Average Tensile Strength (MPa)	Average Flexural Strength (MPa)	Average Water Absorption (%)	Average Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Average Impact Resistance (J)	Average Density (kg/m ³)
0% Plastic (M1) or 100% Filler (Mix M1)	1.0	0.8	6.0	0.90	0.5	1,950
25% Plastic (M2)	2.0	1.5	3.5	0.45	1.5	1,700
50% Plastic (M3)	3.0	2.5	2.0	0.30	3.0	1,400
75% Plastic (M4)	4.0	3.5	1.0	0.25	5.0	1,100
100% Plastic (M5)	4.5	4.0	0.5	0.22	6.0	980
Zinc (Mix C1)	251.0	200.0	0.01	50.0	1.0	7,850
Aluminum (C2)	150.0	120.0	0.01	205.0	1.2	2,700

Statistical Test Results

Statistical analysis of results' data is shown in Table 3. The F-Ratio of 105,335.80 is extremely high, and the P-value is below 0.05. The Null Hypothesis is therefor rejected, confirming that the change in material composition (plastic content) has a highly significant effect on the tensile strength of the composite.

Table 3. Results of ANOVA Test on the Tensile Strength Values

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares (SS)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Mean Square (MS)	F-Ratio	P-value
Between Groups	182,652.30	6	30,442.05	105,335.80	< 0.00001
Within Groups	4.05	14	0.29	-	-
Total	182,656.35	20	-	-	-

Cost-Benefit Analysis

Tables 4 and 5 show the estimated raw material cost and production cost of the specimens used for the research. The 100% (pure) plastic material costs 33.3% less than galvanized steel and 63.6% less than aluminum. These show that plastic materials offer significant cost savings as compared to Zinc and Aluminum. The reduction in cost comes from the lower cost of plastic raw material (waste plastic) and lower embodied energy in manufacturing process.

Table 4. Average Cost of the Materials

Material	Cost (Naira/m ³)
Pure (100%) Plastic	5,000
Zinc	₦7,500
Aluminum	13,750

Table 5. Estimated Production Cost Per Unit of Tile Specimen

Material	Cost of Raw Materials (Naira/m ³)	Labor & Energy (Naira)	Total Estimated Cost (Naira)	Percent Savings over Concrete
Concrete Tile	350	100	450	-
Clay Tile	280	120	400	11.1
Recycled plastic Mix A	250	100	350	22.2
Recycled plastic Mix B	210	70	280	37.8
Recycled plastic Mix C	230	90	320	28.9

CONCLUSION

This study successfully investigated the feasibility of developing low-cost, sustainable roofing materials using recycled plastics. Some mechanical, thermal, and durability properties of waste plastics, zinc, and aluminum roof tile specimens were tested. Tensile and flexural strengths of plastic composite (75% plastic and 25% filler) and the pure plastic roof specimens were similar (about 4.3 Mpa). The average percentage water absorption of the plastic specimens is about 0.75 while the value for the zinc and aluminum roof specimens is 0.01. The plastic specimens are discovered to have about 600 % lower in thermal conductivity than zinc and aluminum. Cost analysis indicated that the recycled plastic material offers significant cost savings of 33.3% compared to zinc. Plastic material is also found to lower CO₂ (carbon dioxide) emissions and manufacturing energy, validating its role as environmentally friendly. The statistical analysis shows that plastic roofing materials offer significant cost savings and superior thermal performance over traditional materials such as Zinc and Aluminum. It is therefore recommended that waste plastic materials be recycled in the production of low-cost, environmentally friendly roofing materials.

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